
CULTURE AND GIRL-CHILD EDUCATION FOR NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A CASE STUDY OF NORTH-CENTRAL NIGERIA

By

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Abstract

This paper examines the issue of culture and girl-child education for national development in Nigeria: a focus on North central states. In a country where women are considered as properties for men and objects for their pleasure, discourages the training of the girl-child in school. The paper further examines some hindrances to effective girl-child education which includes biogrammar factors, misunderstanding of the position of religion on education, socio-economic status of parents, socio-cultural factors, low stereotyped status of girls in the society and school and the patriarchal attitude involving domestic division of labour. Primary and secondary data were collected and analyzed. The finding of this paper is grounded in the fact that cultural sentiments and religious beliefs are the main factors responsible for the low level of the girl-child education in North Central Nigeria. For any meaningful and sustainable development to be attained, the girl-child and by extension women who constitute more than half of Nigeria's population should be given appropriate education and empowerment. The paper posits also the need for effective collaboration and synergy among government and her agencies, interventionist, social agencies and the transitional institutions, for girl-child education for national development.

Key words: Biogrammar, culture, girl-child, national development, education.

Introduction

Literature is full of legends or myths on the evolution of the human race. According to Okunola (2017), the Bible records that the first man Adam was created from the dust and put in the Garden of Eden. The story according to him was confirmed by Prophet Mohammed in Hadith. The Bible records that a rib was taken from Adam's ribs when he was in a deep slumber and that rib was made into another person who Adam named woman; because she was taken out of man. This according to the Bible was the origin of the opposite gender – the girl-child/female and of gender distinction, over the ages; relationship between man and woman has been marked by gender discrimination, stereotype beliefs and notions. The girl-child is regarded as the weaker sex, home maker, the house hold dredge, the producer of children and so on and so forth. According to Okunola (2017) religious and cultural commitment contributes to the idea of discrimination against the girl-child.

Discrimination against the girl-child has usually been accentuated by culture, customs, traditions and beliefs which often are intolerably expensive. Considering some Biblical injunctions as quoted below: -

Your desire shall be for your husband and he shall rule over you. Husband is the head of the wife, let wives also be subject in everything to their husbands. Women submit yourself unto your own husband (The Holy Bible, Gen:3:16; Ephesians 5:22).

The above may be looked at as interpretation of the Holy Scriptures for discrimination against the girl-child especially when it comes to educating man. For religious purposes, women in a number of countries have to wear veil and remain at home not having the opportunity of going to school especially in the Northern part of the country.

Another wide range discourse among sociologists as to why the girl-child are being looked down on is the human "biogrammar" which makes the male more dominant and aggressive as compared to the girl-child (Tiger and Fox, 2006). As a result, the girl-child is expected to stay indoor while the male counterparts are expected to go out and indulge in difficult task which involves going to school for education, closely related to the above is some dangerous and retrogressive cultural practices that provides grounds for the exploitation and deprivation of the girl-child in achieving her maximum development potentials (Mgbogu and Isaku, 2020). They claimed that in our society and individual communities; certain practices, no matter how well intentional still pose a threat on the empowerment of the girl-child and their integration into national development process. According to Mgbogu and Isaku (2020), some of these sharp cultural practices include female genital mutilation, preference for male child over the female gender, even the traditional breaking of kola in the Eastern part of the country which prevents the girl-child from affirming their full potentials. In turn, these cultural practices make the girl-child inferior to her male counterpart and prevent her from attaining her full potentials. In turn, these cultural practices make the girl-child inferior to her male counterparts and prevent her from attaining sustainable development.

The role of the girl-child cannot be overemphasized if all round sustainable development is to be attained in the country. According to Okunola (2017), humanity is like a bird with two wings – one is the man the other is a woman, unless both wings are strong and impelled by some common force, the bird cannot fly heaven ward. God has created all creatures in couples – man, beast, or vegetable all the things of these three kingdoms are of two sexes and there is absolutely equality between them (Okunola, 2017). The girl-child is very important part of society and so need to be empowered through education. The inequality of men and

women and various discriminations against the girl-child is detested by women liberation movement dating back to the days of Mary Wollstonecraft (1792) advocating that women be given broader education for the business of life. Okunola (2017). There are several Non-governmental Organizations (NGO's) that are fighting the course of the girl-child; prominent of the international Non-governmental Organization (NGO) is the Plan International.

The Plan International Publication (2016); gave details of their roles and activities in advancing children's right and equality for girls all over the world. It recognizes the power and potential of every girl-child. But this is often suppressed by poverty, violence, exclusiveness and determination and it is girls who are most affected. According to the report, as an implementing development humanitarian organization, they work alongside children, young people and sympathizers to tackle the root causes of the challenges facing girls and all vulnerable all over the world including Nigeria (Plan International Publication 2016). They support children right from birth until they reach adulthood and enable children to prepare for responds to crisis and adversity. They drive changes in practice and policy at local, national, and global levels using their rich experience and knowledge for over 75 years, they have been building powerful partnership for children and they are active in over 70 countries – Nigeria inclusive.

The Nigerian government and her interventionist agencies are also working to see to the end of all forms of the girl-child discrimination. Ewrierhoma (2002) confirms the fact that government transformed to become a full government ministry (the commission for women) to come to terms with the changing roles and status of the girl-child. The numbers of NGO's concerned with the girl-child issues continue to grow by the day. This has helped many girls to come to terms with their changing roles mainly as dependents, wives and mothers, to income generating ones, complementing the roles of husbands and father within and outside the home.

Conservatism of traditions/culture, coupled with poor understanding of the true injustice as it affects religion is yet another phenomenon which government and her agencies are battling with in this direction. Change is not easy to come by when it comes to issues of tradition and culture. Mahuta (2017) corroborates this by saying that formal education on the part of girls according to some locals, will Europeanize them therefore becoming alienated, disobedient and morally corrupt. In other words, girls would deviate from their culture and tradition closely related to this according to Mahuta (2017) is misconception of religious injunctions which has posed and still posing a big threat in the plight of girl's education particularly in the Northern part of the country.

Despite the campaign by the Federal Government, United Nation Children Education Fund (UNICEF) and stakeholder's in education to improve girl-child education in Nigeria, the level of discrimination on girl-child is still high. Consequently, the paper seeks to re-address the challenges that negate the effectiveness of girl-child education in Nigeria as a whole and the North Central States in particular.

The Problem

The girl-child and indeed women the world over, especially in Africa and Nigeria and particularly in North Cultural Nigeria has had their destiny sealed from birth by tradition and culture on account of their biological sex. They have been called the weaker sex in order to justify societal discrimination and aggression against them. They must remain silent, as hewers of wood and fetcher of water, bearers of children and toilers of arduous labor from sun-rise to sun-down. They can be seen but not to be heard in both the private and the public spaces of decision making. The girl-child by natural status ascribed to her by male defined

norms of societal conduct and behavior remains a property to be owned and commoditized. Consequently, her rights are circumscribed by tradition, customs and the chauvinism of male patriarchy.

The evidence is overwhelming that the girl-child in Nigeria has worldwide recognition and acknowledged inalienable rights as a member of the human family. Statistics have shown that those rights have been and are still being violated by different persons and organizations. Responding to this global threat, numerous persons and groups in acknowledging the continued violation of the rights of the girl-child in Nigeria have called for the intervention of the government and international agencies to address the issue. Nwakoby and Ihediuche (2023).

Illiteracy has been the greatest cankerworm which has eaten deeply in us and elevated the implementation of various wonderful policies of developing countries; illiteracy has a positive relationship with poverty. Unfortunately, illiteracy is highly rated among the girl-child than men which mean illiterate mothers will raise illiterate daughters who are most likely to marry early and have no access to education if their husbands do not comply. The girl-child often faces discrimination from the earliest stages of life through childhood into adulthood. Her low status is reflected in the denial of fundamental needs and rights and in such harmful attitudes and practices as a preference for sons, early marriage, female genital mutilation, domestic abuse, incessant sexual exploitation, and discrimination, less food and less access to education. Balagbogbo (2022).

In many parts of the developing societies namely African, Asia and Latin American countries, the problem of the girl-child marginalization by men economically, educationally, politically and otherwise is a frightening reality, Adama (2017). To ignore the vintage population of the girl-child that constitute half of the Nigerian population is a great problem in itself Lamidi (2012), Olorunfemi (2017) corroborate this in his analysis that national economic development is dependent upon the women of Africa and cannot easily take place without them according to him, a person does not walk far or fast on one leg, how can we expect half of the people to be able to develop a nation yet the reality is that the girl-child are usually left aside when development needs are discussed. Olorunfemi (2017). The girl-child's education must not be regarded as an irrelevance that ends up in the kitchen. It is an imperative for development. Obasanjo (2013).

According to (Heideman and Ferguson 2022), the Beijing document justified the need for a special action platform for girls/women by enumerating the significant cultural and institutional barriers that prevent girls/women from developing their full potentials. According to Heidemann and Ferguson, (2022), the development of any nation demands effective participation of its men and women at social, economic, political and cultural levels of activities. For this purpose, all individuals must be prepared for a condition which requires equitable access to basic resources of education, employment, economic and political power. A conglomeration of literate and illiterates. It is in this regard that literacy is cardinal to the full integration of men and women for the development of the nation; consequently, the girl-child should be empowered through qualitative education for all round and sustainable development. Heinemann and Ferguson, (2022).

Questions

Certain issues elicit suitable answers towards putting this study in proper perspective as follows: -

- ❖ What role do human biogrammar, culture and other gender discrimination have over the girl-child in accessing quality education?

- ❖ Will the empowerment of the girl-child's education reality lead to all round and sustainable development of the country?
- ❖ What level and mode of synergy and cooperation exist against the government interventionist agencies and the traditional institution in reducing the non-accessibility of girl-child education in the country?

Objectives

- This study aims at identifying all forms of dangerous and retrogressive cultural practices that provides ground for the exploitation and deprivation of the girl-child in achieving her maximum development potentials through deprivation of education.
- It aims at identifying how the girl-child can be properly main-streamed and integrated into the national development process through qualitative education which leads to all round and sustainable development
- It aims at identifying ways and manner proper synergy and cooperation among the government intervention agencies and the traditional institution work to curb this menace of depriving the girl-child qualitative education in the country.
- It aims at identifying the various prospects and advantages attached to encouraging the girl-child education in the country.

Significance

This research focuses on the impact of culture on the girl-child education. Culture on its own consists of the semi total of skills, beliefs, knowledge and products that are commonly shared by a number of people and transferred to the children. Through culture; we learn to communicate with one another and to behave in certain ways. Olorunfemi (2017ed). From the following, it shows that the issue of the girl-child deprivation from accessing quality education depends on cultural, beliefs of the people in question. The general belief is that the girl-child is being dominated as a result of the patriarchal practices, cultural, traditional and religious beliefs of the Nigerian society as a whole. However, it varies from one society or area to another. This study focuses on the probability and degree of deprivation in each of the area covered; it goes to show the real reason why the girl-child is being deprived quality education in the area covered.

The missing link noted here is that most often than not, the government, interventionist agencies and the traditional institutions are not really collaborating to fight this problem. Consequently, the research work fashions out an effective synergy and collaboration among the three stake holders in tackling this social menace of depriving the girl-child in accessing quality education that leads to sustainable development. However, during the process of research work some challenges were faced, paucity of funds, language barriers, misinterpretation and misconception of research questions, cultural mindset affecting ;the girl-child research work gives future researcher's specific details on modalities of effectively facing this problem.

Material and Method

The basic means and method adopted for collection of data for processing, analysis and dissemination constitute the method of research. Materials for this research were gathered through quantitative and qualitative methods. The desired area of focus for this research work was Kwara, Kogi and Plateau. The target groups for interview were internally displaced persons, traditional rulers, children of school age, (both males and females), out-of-school children, (girls especially), market woman, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), students in Higher Institutions, some selected personality in the community and relevant stake holders. Relevant government establishments like the Ministry of Education at the state

level, Local Government Education Authority (LGEA), National Orientation Agency (NOA), selected house girls and other critical organizations targeted.

Secondary sources relied upon for this work includes, the views of scholars or researchers, periodicals, text books, academic journals, relevant Google pages, etc. The primary source of information involves the usage of well-designed questionnaires administered to respondents. In addition, the researchers had direct interview with selected respondents in order to get first-hand information from them on the subject matter. The questionnaire was simply structured for easy response. A total of one hundred and eighty (180) questionnaires were administered across the three (3) states.

Concept and Theory

Biogrammar

Looking at one of the reasons why the girl-child is being relegated and looked down upon thereby depriving her qualitative education is the biogrammar factor. According to Tiger and Fox (2006) social scientists assume that human beings behave simply in terms of the culture of their society. Ignoring what they call the human biogrammar. The biogrammar is genetically based; in particular these result from differences between male and female hormones. These differences are due partly to genetic inheritance from man's primate ancestors, partly to a genetic adaptation to hunting way of life. Male's hunt which is an aggressive activity. They are responsible for the protection of the band and for alliance or war with other bands. Thus, men monopolize positions and power. The man and female biogrammar of incentive existence continues in modern industrial society. In summary, biogrammar stands for all forms of retrogressive gender discrimination stereotype, the girl-child/female which debars them equal rights in accessing quality education Tiger and Fox (2006).

Culture

Culture according to Evwierhoma (2002) is a multifarious way which individual employ to come to terms with their environment and the factors within it. This can be regarded to mean man's consciousness as an individual and his role in affirming this consciousness through his beliefs, ways of life and norms in a generally acceptable manner. Culture is an acquisition transferred from individuals to individual and from generation to generation. It shows that culture depends on its practitioner. This means that the issue of the girl-child/female deprivation of quality education and harmful traditional practices depends on the various culture and environment. Alonge Olugasa and Onwuka (2019). In their text, corroborates this that culture/tradition refers to the beliefs, values, legends, customs and information among a group of people that is passed down from one generation to the other by word of mouth or by practice. Culture/traditional practices reflect the values and beliefs held by members of a community for many generations.

Every social group in the world has specific culture/traditional practices and beliefs. Some of these cultural/traditional practices are beneficial to members while some are not. Most of those practices are harmful to a specific group e.g. the girl-child. These practices inflict both immediate and long-term mental and physical pain on the girl-child. These practices also violate the right of the girl-child. According to Alonge, Olugasa and Onwuka (2019). Nigeria is bedeviled with a number of these cultural/traditional practices which includes female genital mutilation, forced marriage instead of going to school, son preference, sex selective, abortion, child marriage, forced pregnancy restriction of second daughter's right to marry, virginity test and date/marital rape etc. All these depend on one's culture or tradition.

From all the above, culture is conceptualized as the sum total of skills, beliefs, knowledge and products that are commonly shared by a number of people and transmitted to the children (Olorunfemi 2017).

Girl-Child Education

There are various definitions of the girl-child and education. Balagbogbo (2022) defines it as a process whereby the girl-child acquires adequate and appropriate, knowledge, skill, attitudes and values in order to function optimally as a citizen. It could also be operationally defined as learning experience organized for the girl-child/female students under the age of 18 in order to make them useful members of the society in which they belong, i.e. to empower them for the future. It could also be defined as programme aimed at giving out of school girls vocational skills to help them break through economically. In summary, the girl-child education is of prime importance in achieving the girl-child health care, faulty planning, economic emancipation, entrepreneur, empowerment and development. Austine and Baje (2015). This education according to Balagbogbo (2022) can be attained through vocational skill acquisition centre, public enlightenment, structures for mobilization and incentives for the girl-child, consequently, Akowe's view (2015) states that education refers to a planned and systematic effort to modify or develop knowledge, skill and attitude through learning, experience, to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities is conceptualized as education.

National Development

The BBC English Dictionary (1992) defines National as relative to the whole of a country rather than a part of it. National here refers to Nigerian as a whole or a country. On the other hand, talking about development is a very wide concept. It has many definitions depending on the meaning intended by the user or researcher. *According to Emezi M. Amadi* in Lamidi (2017), development involves progressions, movement and advance towards something better; it is the improvement on the material and non material aspects of life. In the opinion of Rodney (1972), development implies increased skill and capacity, greater freedom, creativity, self-discipline, responsibility and material well-being.

Consequently, national development is conceptualized to mean the ability of the nation to provide the existence of buoyant economy and availability of social infrastructural facilities for the producer. It is an improvement in all ramifications of a national life. Development in the society needs every one's contribution to fuel its growth (be it male or female). It is an incontestable fact that one head cannot perfect sensitive jobs but two good heads are better than one for the fast development, especially in a developing nation like Nigeria.

Theoretical frame work

A theory represents a unique way of perception of reality expressing someone's prominent insight about an aspect of a phenomenon. In addition to a fresh and new understanding about it (Ikeayinbe 2014). It is a set of statements of propositions that seek to explain or predict kind of explanation. Consequently, the empowerment theory is used as the basis of explaining and analyzing the girl-child deprivation of accessing quality education and its effect on national development.

The empowerment theory was propounded by Solomon (1976). Empowerment according to Uche and Uche (2014) is the ability of individual to gain control socially, politically, economically and psychologically through access to information, knowledge and skills, decision making and individual self-efficacy, community participation and perceived control. According to Robins, Chatterjee and Canda as cited in Uche and Uche (2014), empowerment is a process by which individuals and groups gain power, access resources and gain control

over their own lives. It enables people to gain the ability to achieve their highest personal and collective aspirations and goals, Solomon (1976) posits that the major assumption of the theory is personal, interpersonal and environmental resources are needed to update the skills, knowledge and motivation of people to achieve valid social roles. According to him, powerlessness and feelings of hopelessness are as a result of the inability to use resources and support to achieve goals. According to him, power blockages produce powerlessness which invariably usurps system energy. Empowerment seeks to help individuals and clients to gain power of decision and action over their own lives by reducing the effect of social and personal blocks to exercising existing power from groups and individuals. According to Solomon (1976), the empowerment theory helps to enhance citizen's participation. He emphasized social work's aspiration to social justice and caring communities, engendering hope and power among people. He went further by stressing the fact that three (3) concepts are central to empowerment. They include developing a more positive and potent sense of self, constructing the knowledge and capacity to *achieve a critical perspective* on social and political realities cultivating resources, strategies and competencies to attain personal and collective goals.

Empowerment theory provides an effective support system for individuals, groups and communities that have been blocked from achieving collective goals. According to Payne (2005), empowerment practice helps individuals and groups to overcome social barriers and self-fulfillment within existing social structures. He concludes that empowerment theory has extensively been used in gender studies with marginalized groups or disadvantaged segments of the community.

Looking at the theory above, it is quite relevant and appropriate to the study or theme of this research work; for the fact that the wrong notions that many Nigerians have about the girl-child being considered as properties for man and objects for their pleasure and how this motive restraint them from training them in schools is captured in the theory. Consequently, the theory represents a unique way of perception of reality expressing someone's prominent insight about an aspect of a phenomenon (Ikeayinbe, 2014).

Literature Review

This section reviews literature on relevant topics for proper analysis and understanding of the research topic. It reviews literature on the following: -

Biogrammar factors affecting the girl-child accessibility to Education

As conceptualized in this research work, biogrammar refers to all forms of retrogressive gender discrimination, stereotype, beliefs and notions that relegates the girl-child which debars them equal rights in accessing quality education (Tiger and Fox 2006). Consequently, the paper reviews literature on this briefly. *Looking at the genesis* of this concept - the biogrammar according to (Tiger and Fox 2006) results from dominance and aggressiveness of the males over females due to genetically based differences in male and female hormones. According to Tiger and Fox (2006), these differences are partly due to genetic inheritance from man's primate ancestors, partly to a genetic adaptation to a hunting way of life. Male's hunt which is an aggressive activity. By comparison, women are programmed by their biogrammar to reproduce and care for the children only. Nature intended mother and child to be together. The mother is totally essential to well-being of the child and unless this close emotional bond obtains, the child will be unable to establish successful relationship in later life. Tiger and Fox argue that male and female biogrammar adapts to sexual division of labour in a hunting society.

Their discovery as they put it “we are wired for hunting”. Compared to cultural change, genetic change is slow. According to them the male and female biogrammar of a hunting existence continues in modern industrial society. Consequently, it follows that attempts to abolish gender roles and replace them with unisex roles, however desirable this may be will go against nature.

The above assertions lead to other dehumanizing beliefs and wrong notions against the girl-child and by extension women, not making them to access quality education. According to Abu, Amana and Rowland (2018), the history of Nigeria’s patriarchal system shows that the girl-child education in Nigeria has been relegated to the background in the area of school enrolment, attendance, completion and transition to higher school especially in Northern part of Nigeria. According to them girls were not properly valued, rather they were relegated to the background and rated as second class citizens merely important for reproduction and the “kitchen” as expressed by Tiger and Fox (2006).

Consequently, the females are expected to stay indoors while the male counterparts are expected to go out and indulge in difficult and hard task which includes going to school for education. Culture and religious institutions are closely related to the issue of human biogrammar as a factor discouraging the girl-child education. According to Sheri, (2006), explains the universal devaluation of women. She explains that it is not biology as such that ascribes, women or the girl-child to their low status in society but the way in which every culture including religion defines and evaluate the girl-child or female biology. Thus, it this universal evaluation changes, then the basis for female subordination will be removed.

Empowering the Girl-Child through Education

Empowerment forms the basis of theory used in this research work. Consequently, this sub section reviews brief literature on empowerment. The effect of illiteracy includes so many social vices in our society which can easily be addressed through improved education (Abu, Amana and Rowland 2018). According to Mgbogu and Isaku (2020), education is known to bring enlightenment and create awareness which cuts across all segments of our contemporary society. Inadequate or lack of education has been identified as one of the factors that promotes the exploitation or deprivation of the girl-child/woman in the society. It is also observed according to them that an imbalance in terms of gaining access to education between the male and female gender with the male gender gaining more access which is arguably due to the social structure of our society. Buttressing the gender imbalance in access to education. According to Mgbogu and Isaku (2020), in their research, shows that in eight (8) Northern States of Nigeria, over 80% of the girl-child and women are unable to read and write compared with 54% for men. According to them, 70.8% of young women aged 20-29 in the North West are unable to read and write. This points to a scary and negative image of the plight of the girl-child and women in Nigeria. When the girl-child cannot have access to basic education, such that will eventually become a woman will be vulnerable to deprivation of her rights. According to them both the girl-child and the boy child must have equal access to education which is seen as their right as enshrined in Article 26 of the universal declaration of Human rights which states that everyone has a right to education. According to them, they summed up their findings by stressing the value of education by saying that “the deprived and exploited girl-child, sums up their opinion that we must be mindful of the advantage education has given us and unite to address the girl-child’s un-equal status.

Okunola (2017) posits that education - formal, non-formal and informal is one of the takeoff pads; others could be social, cultural, economic and political. In this regard according to Okunola (2017), the education of the girl-child is an investment which yields dividends to themselves, the generality of the families and the nation regardless of whether or not they

enter the conventional labour force market. And when they do, it certainly creates increase productivity. Aggrey J.K. as cited in Okunola (2017), creates an epigram - “educate a man and you educate a unit, educate a woman and you educate a family”. There are however some factors militating against the girl-child enrolment in school according to Mangvivat and Abama as cited in Abu, Amana and Rowland (2018) as economic hardship or financial constraints, early marriage for girls, historical and community factors societal perception of female roles, child labour high opportunity cost, distance of schools and lack of community support and cultural bias. According to them, this is seen to be more pronounced in Northern Nigeria. Consequently, the next section of this research focuses on the analysis of data gathered from some selected states in North Central Nigeria to confirm or reject as the case may be the above assertions.

Data presentation and Analysis

Data collected for the questionnaires were descriptively analyzed and used to interrogate the research objective.

From the one hundred and eighty (180) questionnaires that were printed and distributed to respondents in Kogi, Kwara and Plateau (147) were completed and returned and they were analyzed.

The respondents’ opinions were sought on issues relating to culture and girl-child education for national developments. A case study of North Central Nigeria.

Question One: Do you agree that the level of the girl-child education in the North Central is low?

Table 1

Opinion	Response	Percentage
Agree	105	71.4%
Disagree	42	28.6%
Total	147	100%

Source: Researcher’s field work, 2025

The above shows that 71.4% of the respondents believe that the level of the girl-child education in the North Central is low.

Question Two: Does culture affects the girl-child education in your community?

Table 2

Opinion	Response	Percentage
Agree	86	59%
Disagree	61	41%
Total	147	100%

Source: Researcher’s field work, 2025

The table above affirms that the cultural outlook in the North Central generally affected the girl-child education.

Question Three: Is there a link between the girl-child education and National development?

Table 3

Opinion	Response	Percentage
Yes	100	68.4%
No	47	32.6%
Total	147	100%

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025

The table above shows that there is obvious link between the girl-child education and National development.

Question Four: Do you agree that the level of the girl-child education in North Central is affected by poverty rather than culture?

Table 4

Opinion	Response	Percentage
agree	49	33.3%
Disagree	98	66.7%
Total	147	100%

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025

The table above shows that culture rather than poverty explains for the low level of girl-child education in North Central Nigeria.

Question Five: Has the education of both the boy-child and the girl-child in other parts of Nigeria accelerated development?

Table 5

Opinion	Response	Percentage
Yes	130	88.4%
No	17	11.6%
Total	147	100%

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025

The respondents suggest that the education of the girl-child in other parts of Nigeria has resulted in development, when compared to North Central states, where there is generally a low level of education of the girl-child.

Question Six: Has cultural beliefs affected the girl-child education in Kogi, Plateau and Kwara?

Table 6

Opinion	Response	Percentage
Yes	115	78.2%
No	32	21.08%
Total	147	100%

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025

Table six (6) reveals that cultural beliefs affected the girl-child education in Kogi Plateau and Kwara and by extension North Central States in Nigeria.

Question Seven: Does the girl-child in the North Central face discrimination as a result of biological features, religious beliefs?

Table 7.

Opinion	Response	Percentage
Yes	125	85%
No	22	15%
Total	147	100%

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025

The analysis of the data shows clearly that the girl-child in the North Central States faces discrimination grounded in physical features and religious beliefs.

Question Eight: Does intervention, Agencies, traditional Institution and Government assist in encouraging the girl-child education for National development?

Table 8

Opinion	Response	Percentage
Yes	57	37%
No	90	63%
Total	147	100%

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025

An analysis of the data shows that the Intervention Agencies have not done enough to encourage girl-child education in North Central States in Nigeria towards accelerating National development.

Findings

The analysis of the data collected from respondents in Kwara, Kogi and Plateau shows clearly that the girl-child in the North Central generally has not been given adequate attention in terms of enrolment in schools.

The enrolment of the girl-child in the North Central States are low mainly because of cultural beliefs, that suggests the girl-child will eventually end up as house wives, that would be catered for by their husbands.

Cultural beliefs, is also the main reason, why the girl-child is not well educated in North Central Nigeria. The analysis of the data also shows that the neglect of girl-child education generally affects National development, since the study further reveals that the girl-child in North Central is not educated generally, not mainly because of poverty, but rather because of reasons grounded in cultural, religious beliefs in North Central States.

The research also shows clearly a low level of intervention by International Agencies, Government at all levels and NGOs towards encouraging girl-child education in North Central Nigeria. Illiteracy of women eventually reduces their contribution to National development in addition; the research shows that the biogrammar factor as raised in the research work is a very significant point why the issue of the girl-child education is low in the North Central part of Nigeria.

Conclusion

This research identified the peculiarity of poor enrolment of the girl-child in school in the North Central Nigeria. Based on findings, it shows that the biogrammar factors still play a significant role in denying the girl-child the right of access to basic education that could lead to sustainable development. The finding shows further that there is weak synergy and cooperation among the government, interventionist agency and the traditional institution in tackling this social menace. Due to the high rate of illiteracy in the North Central Nigeria as it affects the girl-child who will eventually become a woman, the rate of development is very low in the North Central Nigeria. This is so for the fact that a conglomeration of literates is incompatible with development. It is in this regard that literacy is cardinal to the full integration of the “boy-child” and the “girl-child” for the development of the Nation.

Recommendation

The National Orientation Agency need to be funded adequately to carry out their role of educating and enlightening the public on the need to erase all forms of negative reasons for debarring the girl-child from accessing quality education. The government through the ministry of women affairs and social development should work out modalities of coordinating the activities of the NGOs by linking them with the traditional institutions at the local levels in tackling this social menace. The spirit of the Beijing declaration should be respected in the appointment of officials especially in the education sector. This will serve as motivating factor in encouraging the girl-child education generally. Budgetary allocation to the schools should be increased to meet the UNESCO recommendation of 25% of National Budgets to take care of the girl-child education in the North Central in particular and Nigeria in general. Scholarship awards should be provided especially for girls from the elementary to post graduate levels in order to encourage parents and girls who may be challenged by paucity of funds.

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